

Horizon Europe (HE-MSCA-PF)

Final Report

UKRI Horizon Europe Guarantee – MSCA-PF

PORTAL SUMMARY REPORT (PART A)

SUMMARY OF THE CONTEXT AND OVERALL OBJECTIVES OF THE PROJECT

Urban Planning can be defined as a **design-oriented practice**. Its focus is on improving our cities liveability through shaping their built and natural environments, while mediating competing spatial demands, and finding a common ground between the interests of different actors (with and without decisional power) that are involved in these processes. In that regard, urban planning requires collecting and analysing data about our cities through **urban analytics**, using this information in an iterative process of **urban design** that explores and evaluates solutions to complex issues. The endpoint of those is, nevertheless, common: to provide **decision-support** to stakeholders while considering options, constraints and conditions of uncertainty. Decision-support in urban planning is dominated by **Data-Driven Strategies (DDS)** and **Model-Driven Strategies (MDS)**. These traditional approaches to decision-support tend to prioritize the collection and organization of large data volumes, as well as on the simulation of models and scenarios, often assuming a linear, informed and rational process of decision-making. However, these technical approaches often fail to consider the *human aspects* of urban planning, lacking a *design thought* and *communication* strategies to engage and involve different stakeholders or communicate about complex trade-offs. Consequently, albeit important, the analytics that these strategies output often lead to information loss, misinterpretation or outright neglect of their results when presented to decision-makers, hindering effective action. **Knowledge-Driven Strategies (KDS)** are increasingly growing in urban planning, as they tend to mitigate these issues by using expert systems that cater for domain-specific information tailored to experts. Still, even though adopting KDS strategies represent an improvement with respect to DDS and MDS, they are still mostly focused on communicating to a single type of expert. The issue is: **urban planning is an interdisciplinary practice and requires tailoring information to individuals (experts and non-experts) with different backgrounds, roles and technical comfort levels.**

Decoding Cities for Informed Decision Making [DECIDE] is a research-through-design project that addresses this issue. It conceptualises a novel framework for urban decision-support, the **Outcome-Driven Strategy (ODS)**, and develops a **Decision-Support System (DSS)** prototype based on its premises. Unlike the consolidated approaches that focus on the *input* (data volume) or the *process* (model complexity), an ODS prioritizes the *outcome* – specifically, the accessibility and interpretation of information/knowledge outputted by the data and models for the end user. An Outcome-Driven DSS is therefore defined by the integration of two specific **Design Components** into a Knowledge-Driven Strategy (KDS) workflow.

1. User/Stakeholder Profiling: Unlike standardized decision-support strategies, an ODS profiles the users and stakeholders (e.g., Politicians, CEOs, Technicians, Citizens) that may use the system to understand their specific objectives, backgrounds, roles in the decisional process, and technical comfort levels. These profiles are created through a supervised and validated **Generative AI Large Language Models** (GenAI-LLM) implementation, that simulates each stakeholder behaviour and thought process, allowing us to design the DSS based on their needs/requirements, even if time constraints do not allow for their direct participation in all steps of decision-support design.

2. Universal Communication Strategies: The DSS is prototyped based on specific stakeholder's profiles needs/requirements. The focus, however, is on Universal Design – or *anyone should be able to use*. Instead of displaying complex data, convoluted dashboards or data maps, an ODS translates the *essential* metrics and provides narratives through an AI companion that is tailored to the user's profile. These narratives are coupled to different visualization models (i.e. dashboards and data maps), ensuring that outcomes can be understood and acted upon.

The project's **objectives** are aligned to transition from technical analytic models to this human-centric design framework:

- **Objective 1:** To produce and evaluate **Multi-Domain Models (MDMs)** that integrate aspects of urban analytics such as network-based movement analysis (pedestrian, cycling, vehicular), socio-economic (household deprivation and crime) and environmental data (hazards and risk). These models were designed to identify "fragility points" and territorial imbalances, serving as examples for the analytical engine for the system – or what can be integrated into urban decision-support.

- **Objective 2:** To prototype a **DSS Framework** based in the **Outcome-Driven Strategy** capable of retrieving the MDM's and communicating urban analytics toward different publics. This system, developed with a universal design approach, lays the foundation for an urban "Digital Twin", that displays assets and data, while also integrated to a platform for "Spatial Storytelling", where these assets and data are dynamically filtered to showcase information, supporting just-in-time scenario evaluations and decisions.

- **Objective 3:** To test the **Outcome-Driven Strategy by evaluating the DSS's** design, efficiency in communication and user-friendliness. This involved testing the DSS's ability to translate complex probability metrics (i.e. urban network analysis and flood hazard analysis) and urban data (i.e. household deprivation; crime) into actionable insights. Several presentations were made to both sector experts, businesses and the general public to showcase the interface and gather feedback on its design and accessibility to diverse stakeholders.

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WORK PERFORMED FROM THE BEGINNING OF THE PROJECT TO THE END OF THE PERIOD COVERED BY THE REPORT AND MAIN RESULTS ACHIEVED SO FAR

DECIDE is structured around three technical work packages that are aligned with the objectives. Together, these provided an integrated approach to conceptualising Outcome-Driven Strategies for urban planning, designing and building a DSS prototype.

1. Work Package 1 – MDMs for Urban Planning: Activities included the construction of a fit-for-purpose database using OpenStreetMap, Census, socio-economic, environmental and empirical datasets. This database served as a basis to produce **Multi-Domain Models (MDM's)**, urban analytics that included network analysis, socio-spatial analysis and disaster-risk analysis, capable of simulating different scenarios. While the models focused mostly on Cardiff (UK), spin-offs were made with other research partners, with studies for Bristol (UK) – focused on urban mobility, Porto Alegre (Brazil) and Pisa (Italy) – focused on urban network performance, catastrophe risk analysis and emergency response. A scoping literature review and grounded theory was also included in this work package to define Outcome-Driven Decision-Support Strategies.

2. Work Package 2 – Prototyping the DSS: This phase focused on the software architecture and functional requirements. Due to constraints in engaging real stakeholders continuously, the project innovated with the use of **Generative AI Large Language Models (Gen AI LLM)** to create "AI User Personas" (e.g., Councillors, CEOs, Technicians). These AI personas simulated the stakeholders' behavior, providing inputs, needs/ requirements and user journeys to guide the DSS's User Interface (UI) and User Experience (UX) design. Main achievements include a functional DSS prototype that features interactive 3D mapping, integrated dashboards and a "Narrative AI" example that translate what is visualised in maps and statistical data into natural language summaries for users.

3. Work Package 3 – Evaluating and Testing the DSS: We validated the DSS prototype through real-world application, business showcases, and stakeholder proxy testing. The testing focused on demonstrating the MDM's and the DSS ability to support "Outcome-Driven" decisions, prioritizing the communication of results over raw data visualization. Main impacts include the use of MDMs to produce models, technical notes and provide emergency response support during 2024 Porto Alegre Floods emergency response, an extreme event affecting Brazil. This production was used by public authorities to guide operational directives and validate interventions; feedback on these actions was also crucial to guide the DSS prototype development. Furthermore, the DECIDE-DSS prototype was presented in the Allianz Climate Risk Award 2025, where it was awarded the first prize, being recognised and acclaimed by the private sector as an innovative approach for urban catastrophe risk assessment and showcasing its potential towards its development and application as a SaaS in business-oriented settings.

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PROGRESS BEYOND THE STATE-OF-THE-ART AND EXPECTED POTENTIAL IMPACT (INCLUDING SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACT AND WIDER SOCIETAL IMPLICATIONS OF THE PROJECT SO FAR).

DECIDE has generated and is poised to generate substantial impact the fields of decision-support for urban planning and urban analytics in the coming years. These can be divided into scientific & technical innovations and in societal impacts:

Scientific Impacts & Empirical Innovations: DECIDE advanced the state-of-the-art in urban decision-support by formalising the **Outcome-Driven Decision-Support Strategy (ODS)**. Derived from Knowledge-Driven Strategies (KDS) this theoretical framework **redefines decision-support for urban planning**, as it integrates stakeholder profiling and universal communication strategies into the KDS decision-support systems design workflow, allowing expert systems to appeal to multiple kinds of users/experts, instead of being designed toward a single expert. ODS approaches bridge the critical gaps between complex urban analytics (data & models) and how users apprehend an employ information in their decision-making. It proposes that tailoring the outcomes' communication to the characteristics of diverse stakeholders – both experts and non-experts – (i.e. subject matter expertise, time availability, willingness to engage, level of priority and decisional power) a fit-for-purpose approach that is crucial to achieving their agency. DECIDE also innovates through using **Supervised Generative AI Large Language Models (GenAI LLM)** to create “User Personas” which represent and simulate stakeholders’ inputs and behaviour, a method that can be transferable to other activities that involve project or product design. This empirical innovation allows to consider stakeholders requirements, needs and evaluations throughout the DSS design process, even when direct human engagement is constrained, allowing for agile software development and prototyping. Furthermore, upon full implementation, the AI User Personas can be used to tailor the DSS data outputs, narratives and responses in accordance with a specific user/expert, improving their experience.

Technical Impact: The project delivered the **DECIDE Decision-Support System Prototype**, an open-source WebGIS application developed in Python. This hybrid application merges dynamic 3D mapping and data visualization, a dashboard-oriented interface – the foundations for a “digital twin” – with projected “Narrative AI” functionalities. The DSS prototype was demonstrated to different stakeholders (i.e. researchers, potential adopters from private & public sectors) to get feedback in its design and functionalities, receiving considerable attention from private businesses involved in insurance and urban analytics demonstrating its potential to transition into spin-offs. Other key technical achievements lie in the development of **Multi-Domain-Models (MDMs)** that were integrated into the DSS prototype. Through a refinement in the visualization of configurational and network measures that estimate urban accessibility, route choice and road redundancy, it was possible to align these metrics with other domains data (i.e. flood hazard, crime and socio-economic deprivation) within the system architecture, providing examples of which domains can be integrated into urban decision-support.

Societal Impact: The societal value of these innovations was demonstrated through DECIDE’s involvement in the 2024 Porto Alegre Floods in Brazil emergency response. There, we applied the first iteration of the MDM’s, along with the initial GIS-based decision-support system, to produce technical notes and communications for the public authorities involved in the catastrophe analysis. The DSS had a crucial role in first and readily identifying the fragile points in the road-network, modelling the accessibility collapse caused by the flooding. Those outputs supported decision-making during the and after the extreme-weather event, guiding the prioritization of interventions and the validation actions taken to preserve what road access remained for the population and first responders. Furthermore, achieving this level of high-visibility, international impact in a non-associated third country is exceptional given that this was awarded as a European Fellowship – which typically focuses on mobility and collaboration within EU Member States or Associated Countries (i.e. the UK) - rather than a Global Fellowship, where collaboration with third countries, such as **Brazil** is expected. This real-world application not only shaped the UI/UX development of the final prototype by proving that urban analytics must be democratized to grant true agency to decision-makers, but it also demonstrated the project’s outstanding capacity to agilely “export” UK-European research excellence and influence policy on a global scale.

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